
JUST MEDICINE ANDROID APPLICATION A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Just medicine application is project by the company Cluebix software pvt. Ltd[1].It will help users to search medicines via location by just one click or swipe of screen. This application ensures quality life which will improve healthcare system. It provides more faster and reliable online access to location of medical stores, medicines with great variety of recommended as well as non prescribed medicines and other healthcare products, easily accessible all over India. Even rural and urban areas can now have access to recent medications. It provides medical store name, its address and contact information. It continues a legacy of 200 years of success in the medical and chemical sciences. It involves secure, effective and reasonable medicinal stores as well as a customer wisdom that is value of user's fidelity. It offers effortless navigation, more modern applications based on health care system, including clinical applications, medicines review for efficacy and safety, and access to information of drug.

KEYWORD: Just Medicine, Cluebix Software, location, m Health, Healthcare, Pharmacy, Vendor, netmeds.com, military, defense, doctors, customer satisfaction, Medication adherence, Research2Guidance, statistic variables, navigation, online access, clinical, fidelity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's hectic schedule of consumer demands an effective and time reducing application system that will accommodate as per their requirement, providing them with useful services at the click of a button or swipe of a screen. With the presence of large number of medical applications available in the market today, it has become clear that users want to be more associated with healthcare concern. There are more than 100,000 applications registered in the healthcare segments of most application platform.

Pharmacology is study of drugs, in which drugs can be classified as artificial and natural. It is a process of connecting chemical research with healthcare research. Also, it offers secure as well as efficient usage of dispensary drugs. Pharmaceutical practices include contemporary functions such as preparing and dispensing medications. Pharmacists are the healthcare specialists on medications and drug remedy and are

the primary experts who suggest medication usage to cure patients to have positive healthcare results. In forthcoming years, it is believed that chemists will be more active within the healthcare network.

Indian dispensary network has ongoing growth rate at 15% since last eight years. From overseas growth, to interior growth, the Indian dispensary industry had a great evolution over the past few years. This expeditious growth is about to bring revolutionary changes in the Indian division network. The crucial difficulties involves restrained development in regulative amendments, highly fragmenting nature of the division network and presence of robust resistance from hallway of shopkeepers included in the supply of dispensary products.

Medication Treatment Organization includes the scientifically detached applications that chemists can offer for their patients. Such applications involve the rigorous scrutiny of all medication (recommended, non-recommended and floral) presently being fetched by a person.

Development in scientific research has always had major impacts in healthcare system. The smartphone is one of the most recent trends in communication, in which user's smartphone can be used for communicating via short message services, email, Internet searches, and using distinct applications. Most of the doctors uses smart phone for treatment on regular basis. The impact of medicine applications has always been significant in medical industry. The research, that is organized every year by Research to Guidance, have found now a days mHealth application broadcasts and aspirants outbalance aims persistent sick patients (33 percent), healthcare and strength oriented users (25 percent) and eventually, medical specialist (16 percent).

The Healthcare network is very versatile in nature, including distinct locations of dispensaries and customers. Increase in usage of smartphones in medical field indicates the growing opportunity for improved access to information, clinical communication, and services at the point of care, or from anywhere at any time.

Just Medicine is an online pharmaceutical mobile application for Indian consumers offering both prescribed and non-prescribed medications based on "location" of consumer. It is a generic software which is used by large variety of citizens and vendors to operate the procedure of physically validating the accessibility of medical products in medical stores. It is life-saving, funds saving and time reducing application which is comfortable to use and offers a better menu driven interface.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This paper [2] proposed one of India's most trusted pharmacies, with over 100 years' experience in delivering quality medicines. It is being helped to accompany our own fitness efficiently as well as reach of loved ones wherever they reside in India. It is most convenient to purchase and deliver medications all over the country – with just swipe of the screen. It involves brisk online accessibility of medications with proper supply of products by clicking at netmeds.com, with large variety of recommended medicines and other healthcare products easily available all over India.

This paper [3] present the recent study was designed to measure the degree of consumer satisfaction and also their purchase habit while shopping in retail dispensaries i.e. independent dispensaries and in network or shopping complex dispensaries. The analysis design is a type of trans-sectional explanatory research using convenient sampling methods. A survey or public – opinion poll was conducted to evaluate the degree of customer satisfaction as well as consumers buying habit in trade dispensaries.

Fig. 1 Satisfaction of customer with product range and its availability

Interrelation between personal satisfaction and consumer purchasing habit in both dispensaries was obtained on the basis of various quality of service (QOS) offered by pharmacy and the product variety along with their accessibility in the pharmaceutical store. It was observed that pharmaceutical store selection habit among customers points that perceptions and image along with individual properties have major impact on the final result.

In paper [4] creator proposed that customer satisfaction is the measure of satisfaction offered by the services or product of a firm as measured by the number of duplicate customers. The primary goal of the research is to find out the consumer satisfaction and allegiance towards Apollo pharmacy store. From the research conducted, it is observed that the statistic variables such as gender ,occupation and age group are having very less impact on the factors of consumer satisfaction.

White paper [5] illustrates that Research Now study indicates:

- 45 percent of healthcare specialist say they will include mobile applications to their practice in the forthcoming six years,
- 87 percent of healthcare experts think that healthcare applications will increment their understanding of patients’ conditions.
- 95 percent of consumers believe health applications will help to enhance their gratification.
- 73 percent of healthcare specialist thinks healthcare applications will inspire patients to take more responsibility for their fitness.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The remarkable problem is patient do not get specific medicines at time during emergency situations due to lack of medicines in medical store. Medication adherence, which refers to the measure or extent to which a consumer takes the correct medicine at the correct time according to the doctor’s recommendation, has now a days appeared as a serious concern because many researchers have said that non-adhesion may negatively affect the consumers, thereby increasing medical costs.

Medication non-adhesion is a frequent and tangled concern which adds to faulty therapy results and utilizes healthcare devices. It needs additional time and efforts when consumers have to search the accessibility of medicines in medical store manually. Thus, to reduce time usage and human efforts the “Just Medicine” mobile application is used for checking the availability of medicines in place of manual search. The objective of this project is to reduce time usage and human efforts and thereby providing user friendly interface.

IV. PROPOSED WORK

Proposed structure contains one private server managed by the company and various customers. At present, people have to search for the accessibility of medicines at different medical stores manually. To find the required medicine is time consuming, thus proper system is required. We need full pledge software to check

the accessibility of medicines at medical stores in the nearby location with the proper knowledge of address of medical store and their contact number.

The proposed system will be helpful to the customers in many ways. It will help them to search medicines in an effective manner. The application can keep an eye on the available medicines. The software is provided with all the master entries to enter any medicine or location and search the listed medical store, its address and their contact number.

V. SURVEY TABLE

S.No	Particulars	Gender	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.	Availability of all types of Medicines	Male	3.75	0.916
		Female	3.72	0.983
2.	Price of medicines	Male	3.62	0.676
		Female	3.53	0.762
3.	Working hours	Male	3.97	1.021
		Female	3.41	1.392
4.	Availability of all company medicines	Male	3.71	0.957
		Female	4.02	0.901
5.	Order booking facility	Male	3.92	0.721
		Female	3.95	0.826
6.	Home delivery service	Male	4.02	0.797
		Female	3.91	0.901
7.	Payment options	Male	3.92	0.753
		Female	3.63	0.938
8.	Sterility and hygiene of the pharmaceutical store	Male	4.18	0.893
		Female	4.34	0.997
9.	Maintenance of medicines at proper temperature	Male	4.23	0.764
		Female	4.21	0.591
10.	Medicines are printed with proper batch date, expiry date, etc.	Male	4.42	0.893
		Female	4.34	

VI. CONCLUSION

Through the research paper entitled, “A review on Just Medicine Application”, it is observed that it will prove handy and useful to people who are in search of medicine. It will reduce human efforts as well as time usage. Also, it will be used in military and defense sectors. This mobile application provides user friendly interface.

Heavy traffic, shop closed, monsoons, lack of vehicle parking, forgetfulness are few accounts that may lead to skimming of crucial medications. Taking medications daily is a detracting constituent of directing continuous clinical situations, so it is important that we must not dry out of vital medicines. By just signing into Just Medicine application, citizens can search medical products without moving from the convenience of our household. It offers easy access to secure, reliable, and safe medications, and also, get to understand everything about the medicine at Just Medicine application.

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